

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF USING INTERNATIONAL PHONETIC ALPHABET SYMBOLS ON GRADE 12 STUDENTS' PRONUNCIATION SKILLS

Caryll Dee Dumanggas¹, Uriel Guerva², Mike Jasper Otero³, Jovenil Bacatan⁴

¹²³⁴Department of Teacher Education, UM Peñaplata College, Island Garden City of Samal 8119, Philippines

¹itsmecarylldee@gmail.com

²urielguerva@gmail.com

³mikejasperotero17@gmail.com

⁴jovenilbacatan@umindanao.edu.ph

Corresponding Author: Jovenil Bacatan, Email: jovenilbacatan@umindanao.edu.ph

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ABSTRACT

The study entitled "The Effectiveness of Using International Phonetic Alphabet Symbols on Grade 12 Students' Pronunciation Skills" aimed to determine the effectiveness of using International Phonetic Alphabet Symbols on the pronunciation skills of Grade 12 students. The study used a pre-experimental research design specifically employing one-group pretest-posttest research design. The essential data were gathered from a sample size of 24 respondents with the aid of a validated research-made questionnaire. Data were analyzed and interpreted using weighted mean and paired t-test as statistical tools. It was found that the Grade 12 students initially struggled with their English pronunciation skills; however, after the intervention, there was an increase in students' scores from the pre-test to the post-test. It was also found that there is a significant difference in the students' pronunciation skills before and after using the IPA symbols. The researchers acknowledged the major limitation, which is the absence of a control group during the study. Nevertheless, the implications of this study would be of interest to the curricularists and the education policymakers in integrating IPA symbols in English language classes. Future researchers were recommended to utilize true experimental research design, which includes control groups and random assignment that can help establish stronger cause-and-effect relationships.

INTRODUCTION

Pronunciation is seen as an alternative talent for utterances, and it is essential to distinguish between speech and elocution. Varasarin (2009) stated that accurate pronunciation is necessary for learning conversational skills in a second language. However, many people who acquire English as an interlanguage still need to improve their pronunciation through repeated study (Gilakjani et al., 2011). Furthermore, phonetic symbols can help students improve their communication skills, make significant meaning of conversations, and beneficially lead them to master pronunciation (Mompean, 2005). It cannot be easy initially, but mastering it will improve pronunciation (Najamudin, 2017).

From the point of view of Morley (1998), pronunciation generally plays a significant role in assisting the learner in becoming an understandable speaker. Biyaem (1997) mentioned that Thai teachers face numerous challenges when teaching English, including the need for English language skills. Additionally, Sukamolson (1989) suggests that Thai students struggle with pronunciation and difficulty listening to dialogues and texts. Thai school curricula cannot meet the demand for English. Listening and speaking are essential skills, but they are not the primary focus of the English curriculum for tertiary education (Wiriyaichitra, 2001).

In connection, Hanumanthappa (2014) stated that Phonetic symbols are necessary for the English language due to the inadequacy of English spelling in conveying word pronunciations. The existing alphabet fails to distinguish between similar sounds, such as the "th" in words like "this" and "that" versus the "th" in words like "thank" and "throw." To overcome these challenges, the intro-

duction of the International Phonetic Alphabet (IPA) is recommended (Jahan, 2011). The IPA employs specific symbols corresponding to each English alphabet to represent pronunciation accurately.

This study analyzed the effectiveness of using IPA symbols on the pronunciation skills of Grade 12 students at UM Peñaplata College. The researcher wanted to conduct this study because there is no existing study in the local community, and they have seen students struggle to pronounce English words. The result of this study can help to the effectiveness of IPA symbols in learning pronunciation and English phonology.

Accordingly, this study aims to determine the effectiveness of using IPA symbols on the pronunciation skills of grade 12 students at UM Peñaplata College. This specifically sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of pronunciation skills of the students before and after using the IPA symbols?
2. Is there a significant difference in pronunciation skills before and after using the IPA symbols?

Upon addressing these research questions through one group pretest-posttest pre-experimental research design, it will be possible to generate how IPA symbols can be integrated early in English language classes and how students have improved their English pronunciation using the IPA symbols. The researchers have acknowledged that this study poses several limitations, such as the absence of a control group during the study and the time allocated for the intervention.

LITERATURE REVIEW

IPA Symbols in General

The International Phonetic Alphabet (IPA) is a system of symbols, often written using Latin characters, that provides a standardized representation of the sounds found in spoken language. It serves as a widely accepted standard in the field of linguistics. However, an American phonetic alphabet was also developed due to difficulty typing IPA symbols using standard keyboards. Using IPA symbols helps reduce errors and eliminates the challenges of deciphering handwritten transcriptions (IEEE Signal Processing Society, 2007).

The IPA was initially developed in 1888 to provide a universal code for accurately representing the pronunciation of sounds in all languages. However, many English as Foreign Language (EFL) students need help to become familiar with the IPA symbols. While phonetic transcription is available in bilingual dictionaries, students often need help to decode the symbols, leading to confusion and difficulties in using them effectively. As many English learners can attest, written English is only an approximate representation of the spoken language. Phonetic transcription, on the other hand, aims to represent each sound precisely and unambiguously, without redundancy or omission (Safari et al., 2013b). In some dictionaries, pronunciation respelling is used instead of IPA symbols, such as in Australian English (AuE), Canadian English (CaE), General American (GA), Indian English (InE), Irish English (IrE), New Zealand English, Received Pronunciation (RP), Scottish English (ScE), South African English (SAE), Standard Singapore English (SSE), and Welsh English (WaE).

Furthermore, the International Phonetic Alphabet consists of 107 letters representing consonants and vowels and 31 diacritics that modify these sounds. Additionally, 19 supplementary signs indicate supra-segmental qualities such as length, tone, stress, and intonation. The IPA symbols underwent revision in 2016, following the guidelines set by the International Phonetic Association (IPA) (Safari et al., 2013b).

The IPA association developed the International Phonetic Alphabet (IPA) in the 19th century, using phonetic characters derived from the Latin alphabet. Its purpose is to establish a standardized representation of spoken language. Professionals widely utilize IPA, including singers, actors, teachers, and others. It serves to identify language characteristics such as intonation, phones, phonemes, and word and syllable separation. The IPA association incorporated additional symbols to represent speech features beyond the primary characters. For instance, extended symbols denote sounds like tooth gnashing and lisping, which involve clefts in the lip and palate (Qadir & Rizwan, 2020).

Furthermore, Qadir and Rizwan (2020) emphasized the importance of IPA symbols in studying a second language. Learners need to familiarize themselves with the IPA symbols to grasp the sounds of English as a second language. Without proficiency in IPA symbols, learners may struggle with listening and spelling. While Knoblock (2007) acknowledged that IPA symbols form a substantial part of phonetics, the significance of IPA in standardizing language pronunciation cannot be overlooked, as IPA symbols are considered the foundational elements of phonetics.

International Phonetic Alphabet (IPA) ,mʌ'næʃn-l fə'netɪk 'ælfə,bet

Consonants (pulmonic)

	Bilabial	Labio-dental	Dental	Alveolar	Post-alveolar	Retroflex	Palatal	Velar	Uvular	Pharyngeal	Glottal
Plosive	p b			t d		ʈ ɖ	c ɟ	k ɡ	q ɢ		ʔ
Nasal	m	ɱ		n		ɳ	ɲ	ŋ	ɴ		
Trill	ʙ			r					ʀ		
Tap or flap		ⱱ		ɾ		ɽ					
Fricative	ɸ β	f v	θ ð	s z	ʃ ʒ	ʂ ʐ	ç ʝ	x ɣ	χ ʁ	ħ ʕ	h ɦ
Lateral fricative				ɬ ɮ							
Approximant		ʋ		ɹ		ɻ	j	ɰ			
Lateral approximant				l		ɭ	ʎ	ʟ			

VOWELS

Figure 1. Consonant, Vowel, and Diphthong

Undoubtedly, the International Phonetic Alphabet is a valuable tool for examination, and in many cases, phonetic transcription can save time and facilitate the teaching of spoken language-related concepts. Those who have not previously used phonetic transcription may need a few hours to learn IPA and understand its basic principles. However, the time and effort invested in learning IPA are quickly compensated through enhanced teaching efficiency. The trend of globalization has further solidified English as the lingua franca, spoken by over 350 million native speakers and 1000-1500 million non-native speakers for daily communication (Katamba as cited in Por & Fong, 2011).

Additionally, communicating in English today can enhance people's mobility, joint study programs, commercial networks, information technology, and more. Well-established dictionaries such as the Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary, Oxford Dictionary of Pronunciation, Cambridge International Dictionary of English, Longman Pronunciation Dictionary, Collins English Dictionary, and others have adopted IPA symbols, which must continue to be utilized. Individuals can correctly pronounce words when referring to phonetic symbols in dictionaries, whether in digital or printed form or on mobile devices (Por & Fong, 2011).

According to Kenworthy (as cited by Jahan, 2011), six primary factors influence pronunciation learning, including native language, age, exposure, phonetic ability, attitude and identity, and motivation and concern for sound pronunciation. Phonetic ability plays a crucial role in pronunciation learning, as stated by Siertsema (2009), who defines *pronunciation* as the act or manner of articulating words, speech utterances, or phrases, precisely conveying the prevalent or commonly understood way of speaking a word, using phonetic symbols.

Moreover, people often utilize digital dictionaries, whether in digital, printed, or mobile phone format, to learn how to pronounce phonetic symbols (Por & Fong, 2011). Many individuals rely on Android or smartphone applications to access their digital dictionaries and acquire correct pronunciation. Teachers should accurately introduce IPA symbols in the language classroom to assist students in independently pronouncing new words (Jahan, 2011). Using phonetic symbols can improve students' communication skills, enable better comprehension of conversations, and effectively guide them in pronunciation learning (Mompean, 2005). Adopting IPA for learning pronunciation may initially present challenges, but mastery of the symbols will ultimately enhance pronunciation skills (Najamudin, 2017).

The IPA Symbols as Pronunciation Skill

Numerous authors strongly recommend that language learners acquire knowledge of the phonetic alphabet, including its symbols and code words representing each sound, especially the International Phonetic Alphabet (IPA). This enables students to transcribe speech sounds from different accents and languages and use phonetic symbols to pronounce new English words accurately. Familiarity with the phonetic alphabet also helps students understand the subtle distinctions and articulation of similar sounds within a given language and across different languages. Educators have observed that employing the phonetic alphabet and providing clear explanations enhances students' awareness of articulation when learning pronunciation. Moreover, the IPA assists students in better understanding the speech sounds used in various alphabets worldwide (Jacob, 2020); cited in (Riza, 2021).

Furthermore, phonetic symbols aid students in improving their communication skills, comprehending conversations more effectively, and guiding them in pronunciation learning (Mompean, 2005). These symbols offer guidance to accurately predict English sounds, allowing students to receive immediate feedback by comparing their pronunciation with the displayed phonetic symbols. Consequently, this boosts their confidence in speaking English and improves their pronunciation skills (Por & Fong, 2011). Unfortunately, some English speakers, particularly native speakers, have developed the habit of misusing certain IPA symbols in a way that can seriously confuse learners from other backgrounds (Fiktorius, 2013).

Phonetic transcription can indicate the correct pronunciation of words by including the phonetic transcription as footnotes in learners' books. However, this method requires instructors and students to be familiar with the IPA or the specific transcription system. Nonetheless, the IPA is relatively easy to grasp, as there is a direct correspondence between written symbols and vocal sounds (Safari et al., 2013b).

On the contrary, the pronunciation learning system encompasses six indicators that describe the role of phonetic symbols based on the previous explanation (Putri, 2016). First, reading phonetic symbols enhances students' autonomy in pronunciation learning. Second, it helps students become more intelligible speakers of English. Third, reading phonetic symbols boosts students' confidence in speaking English. Fourth, phonetic symbols can sometimes pose a burden for students. Fifth, teaching phonetic symbols is an integral part of teaching English. Sixth, reading phonetic symbols aids students in learning pronunciation.

Additionally, according to Dalton and Seidlhofer (1994), pronunciation involves producing and perceiving the sounds of a language to convey meaning in different language contexts. It encompasses segmental sounds, stressed and unstressed syllables, and speech melody, which are influenced by voice quality, speech rate, and loudness. Even in a simple two-syllable phrase like "Hello!" all these aspects are present simultaneously from the start of our speech.

The Oxford Dictionary defines *pronunciation* as how a language, specific word, or sound is spoken. Within a particular dialect, "correct pronunciation" can vary among individuals. Different people or groups may pronounce a word differently depending on their birthplace, current residence, speech or voice disorders, ethnic group, social class, or education level. Learning pronunciation in a language involves two main steps, as Fraenkel (1984) outlined. The receptive or listening stage teaches students to recognize significant sounds and patterns in the language. In contrast, the formative or speaking stage focuses on students learning and producing what they have learned.

As mentioned by Celce-Murcia et al. (2010) advocated for a communicative model of pronunciation teaching, which emphasizes metacognitive knowledge, perceptual abilities, controlled practice activities for producing new sounds, integrating pronunciation with meaning, and mechanical skills in pronouncing while engaging in the communicative practice. Traditional pronunciation teaching often relies on face-to-face instruction and drills. Research by Kim (2012) indicated that visual feedback can help students improve their pronunciation as it considers their activities, context, and cultural background.

Synthesis

The International Phonetic Alphabet (IPA) is widely used in linguistics; however, many English as a Foreign Language (EFL) learners struggle. Phonetic transcription is crucial for precisely representing spoken language, and dictionaries often use it. Learning the IPA symbols can enhance pronunciation skills, and students need to become familiar with them. The benefits of IPA symbols include better articulation awareness, clear explanations, and the ability to transcribe speech sounds from different accents and languages. Despite its value, some native speakers misuse IPA symbols, confusing learners. Phonetic transcription with footnotes in the learner's books can help, but it requires familiarity with IPA. Pronunciation learning depends on six factors, including phonetic ability, and learning IPA symbols enhances autonomy in pronunciation. It also improves student's intelligibility and confidence in speaking English. While it can pose a burden, teaching IPA symbols is integral to English instruction.

METHOD

Research Design

The study employed a quantitative, pre-experimental research design, specifically a one-group pretest-posttest design, where a single case is observed at two time points, one before the treatment and one after the treatment. Changes in the outcome of interest are presumed to be the result of the intervention. According to Creswell (2009), quantitative research is a type of educational research that involves specific, narrow inquiries, the collection of measurable data from participants, statistical analysis of the

data, and an unbiased and objective approach to the investigation. It employs statistical techniques to comprehend and explain phenomena. In the context of this study, the pre-experimental design was employed as a stepping stone for more rigorous experimental design in the future. It is useful when researchers are developing new interventions, testing out new measurement instruments, or want to build toward more rigorous experimental designs (The Research Methods Consortium, 2022).

Specifically, this study utilized the one-group pretest-posttest design. It does not have a comparison group; everyone who takes part in the research receives the intervention. Controlling for extraneous variables is difficult or impossible in this design, but given that it is possible to establish some measure of time order, it can begin to provide potential support for causality (The Research Methods Consortium, 2022).

Research Respondents

As Ary et al. (2010) defined; the population refers to all individuals, events, or objects belonging to a specific and well-defined class. In this study, the respondents comprised 24 students from Grade 12-HUMSS (Humanities and Social Sciences) of UM Peñaplata College. The study conducted by Atkins et al. (2022) included 15 participants using a pre-test and post-test design and found significant results.

The researchers selected senior high school students, specifically those in Grade 12-HUMSS, as they believed these students would provide the necessary data for the study. According to the Senior High School Curriculum Guide from the Department of Education (DepEd), HUMSS students are expected to develop their listening and speaking skills, focusing on effective communication in various situations and enhancing their articulation and modulation when delivering speeches. It was found by the Philippine Institute for Development Studies (PIDS) research that senior high school students in the Philippines have weak English speaking and writing skills, as evidenced by their reports and written outputs (Bermudez, 2020). This gave the reason for the researchers to select the respondents mentioned above.

Research Instrument

Data plays a crucial role in the study as it is necessary to provide support and evidence for the research. The main objective of the study is to assess the effectiveness of utilizing IPA symbols on the pronunciation skills of Grade 12 students at UM Peñaplata College, and the collected data will be utilized to interpret and analyze the results. The study employs an instrument known as an objective test to facilitate the interpretation of the data. Objective tests assess the ability to recall facts and comprehend course materials. These tests typically require independent thinking, high-level critical reasoning, and the ability to make precise distinctions to determine the most suitable answer. Objective test questions include multiple-choice, true-false, and matching items (Tavakol & Dennick, 2011).

Furthermore, tests are valuable measuring tools in educational research, particularly in assessing students' abilities in specific subjects. Ibrahim and Wahyuni (2012) define a *test* as a tool or procedure used to measure something according to prescribed rules and methods. As Ary et al. (2010) explained, a test presents stimuli or questions to individuals to elicit responses based on which numerical scores can be assigned. It measures skills, knowledge, intelligence, abilities, or talents individuals or groups demonstrate.

First, multiple choice questionnaires (MCQ) were used in the study, which can effectively and efficiently assess the effectiveness of IPA Symbols on the Pronunciation Skills of Grade 12 Students, with several potential advantages. The MCQ test consists of 30 questions, with each item worth one point. The questions used in the pre-test were the same as in the post-test to determine the effectiveness of using IPA symbols on the pronunciation skills of Grade 12 students.

Second, the researchers used rubrics adapted from Henrichsen's rubric (n.d.a.) for the pronunciation test. They allocated a numerical value to a piece of work or performance using rubrics, which are descriptive scoring systems. Using IPA symbols on the pronunciation skills of Grade 12 students, the researcher assigned a rating or score to a complex pronunciation test. Furthermore, researchers described a set of characteristics representing an underlying performance continuum to this set of guidelines or criteria. The pronunciation rubric has four criteria and five rating scale categories resulting from the marking system: intonation, vowels, consonants, and word stress. Each criterion contributes to the total reliability of these twenty points out of five points for each criterion. See the table below (Pronunciation rubric).

Pronunciation Rubric

Category	Vowels	Consonants	Intonation	Word Stress
5	Pronounces vowels correctly all the time.	Pronounces consonants correctly all the time	Uses rising or falling intonation appropriately all the time. Uses intonation to express various meanings, such as apology, sarcasm, etc.	Places stress on the right syllable of multisyllabic words all the time

4	Pronounces vowels correctly most of the time.	Pronounces consonants correctly most of the time.	Uses rising or falling intonation appropriately most of the time but sometimes ineffectively.	Places stress on the right syllable of multisyllabic words most of the time but misplaces it on a few words
3	Makes inconsistent vowel errors. Common errors: /i:, ɪ/	Makes inconsistent consonant errors. Common errors: /w, v/ /s, z/	Uses rising or falling intonation appropriately most of the time, but intonation impedes understanding.	Places stress on the right syllable of multisyllabic words most of the time, but misplaces it on certain words
2	Pronounces some vowels incorrectly consistently. Common errors: /e, ɪ/, /e, eɪ/ /ɑ:, aɪ/	Pronounces some consonants incorrectly consistently. Common errors: /f, h/, /t, d/, /k, g/	Uses intonation appropriately sometimes to express emotion, but uses up-rising intonation for both questions and yes/no questions.	Places stress on the right syllable of multisyllabic words most of the time, but misplaces it on a large number of words
1	Vowel errors are frequent. Common errors: /e, æ/, /æ, ʌ/ /æ, ɒ/, /ʌ, ɔ/ /ɔ, əʊ/	Consonant errors are frequent. Common errors: /p, b/, /p, f/ /m, n/, /n, l/ /l, r/	Uses rising or falling intonation inappropriately frequently.	Frequently misplaces stress on multisyllabic words

Third, the study used a Likert scale to assess the parameters of the indicators, from 1 to 5, with the minimum score/worst value being 1 and the maximum/best value being 5. The pre-test and post-test mean scores set limits for a descriptive equivalent scale. Its interpretation was based on the Policy Guidelines on Classroom Assessment for the K to 12 Basic Education Program (DO 8, s. 2015) and Guidelines on the Assessment and Rating of Learning Outcomes Under the K to 12 Basic Education Curriculum (DO 73, s. 2012).

Likert Scale Parameter Limits

(Based on DepEd Order No. 8, s. 2015 and DepEd Order No. 73, s. 2012)

Scale	Range of Test Scores	Descriptive Equivalence	Interpretation
5	42.00 – 50.00	Outstanding	This means that the student at this level exceeds the core requirements in terms of knowledge, skills, and understandings, and can transfer them automatically and flexibly through authentic performance tasks.
4	38.00 – 41.99	Very Satisfactory	This means that the student at this level has developed the fundamental knowledge and skills and core understandings, and can transfer them independently through authentic performance tasks.
3	34.00 – 37.99	Satisfactory	This means that the student at this level has developed the fundamental knowledge and skills and core understandings and, with little guidance from the teacher and/or with some assistance from peers, can transfer these understandings through authentic performance tasks.
2	30.00 – 33.99	Fairly Satisfactory	This means that the student at this level possesses the minimum knowledge and skills and core understandings, but needs help throughout the performance of authentic tasks.

1	Below 30.00	Did not meet expectations	This further means that the student at this level struggles with his/her understanding; prerequisite and fundamental knowledge and/or skills have not been acquired or developed adequately to aid understanding.
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RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Level of Pronunciation Skills of the Students before and after Using the IPA Symbols

Table 1 shows the pre-test mean scores of experimental groups in the test questionnaire and pronunciation test. The study has twenty-four (24) respondents in one experimental group, seven males and seventeen females, aged between 17 to 18 years old. The pre-test mean value is 29.92, and the standard deviation is 2.39. It has a descriptive equivalence of *did not meet expectations*. The study shows that the student at this level struggles with his/her understanding; prerequisite and fundamental knowledge and skills have not been acquired or developed adequately to aid understanding. English learners from diverse backgrounds and nationalities often encounter challenges when it comes to pronouncing words accurately and require assistance in learning the English language. These learners may seek support in various areas, such as pronunciation, grammar, semantics, and other aspects of the language (Bian, 2013).

Moreover, students' first language significantly influences their target language pronunciation and is a crucial factor in determining English accents. The phenomenon known as interference from the first language can result in errors related to aspiration, stress, and intonation in the target language. Students may encounter challenges articulating English words due to the strong influence of similar sounds in their native language (Yule, 2002).

Table 1. *Level of Pronunciation Skills of the Students before and after Using the IPA Symbols*

	N	Mean	SD	Descriptive Equivalent
Before Using IPA Symbols (Pre-test)	24	29.92	2.39	Did not meet expectations
After Using IPA Symbols (Posttest)	24	37.88	4.05	Satisfactory

As suggested by Jahara and Abdelrady (2022), a significant factor contributing to the limited pronunciation skills of English learners is insufficient exposure to an authentic English-speaking environment that enables them to acquire accurate pronunciation concurrently. Moreover, many students must begin learning a second language after acquiring their mother tongue. To address the psychological barriers and other difficulties, teachers can approach pronunciation instruction with the objective of helping students grasp the essential elements of spoken English, allowing others to comprehend them quickly rather than focusing on achieving native-like pronunciation (Gilbert, 2008).

However, the mean value for the post-test is 37.88, and the standard deviation is 4.05. It has a descriptive equivalent of *satisfactory*. This means that the students have developed the fundamental knowledge, skills, and core understandings with little guidance from the teacher and with some peer assistance. As Brown (1992) stated, providing comprehensive instruction on phonetic symbols offers several benefits to students. It assists them in recognizing spelling variations, understanding different sounds, identifying word stress patterns, and comprehending idiomatic expressions. After receiving instruction on phonetic symbols, students gain various advantages. They become more confident in enhancing their communication skills, engaging in meaningful conversations, and effectively learning pronunciation (Mompean, 2005).

Moreover, this finding is consistent with previous research that has also demonstrated the effectiveness of IPA symbols in improving learners' pronunciation skills in English. One study by Lee and Jang (2015) examined the effects of IPA-based instruction on the phonetic pronunciation skills of Korean learners of English. The study found that using IPA symbols helped learners improve their accuracy in producing English sounds and their ability to distinguish between similar English sounds. The study also found that using IPA symbols helped learners better understand English phonetics and apply this knowledge to their pronunciation practice.

Another study by Kormos and Dénes (2004) investigated the use of IPA symbols in teaching English pronunciation to Hungarian learners of English. The study found that using IPA symbols helped learners improve their pronunciation accuracy in English. Specifically, the study found that learners who were taught using IPA symbols showed more remarkable improvement in their pronunciation accuracy than learners who were taught using traditional methods of teaching pronunciation. Hence, students who have reached a certain level of proficiency in a language, particularly at the beginner level, should have acquired fundamental skills and knowledge in pronunciation. By providing explicit instruction and opportunities for practice and feedback, learners can develop accurate pronunciation habits that support advanced language development (Gregersen & Rubin, 2010).

Significant Difference in Pronunciation Skills before and after Using the IPA Symbols

The results illustrated in Table 2, the comparison of mean scores of the pre-test and post-test, show a mean difference of 7.96, demonstrating the effectiveness of IPA on pronunciation skills. The computed t-value of 12.466 and p-value of 0.000 with a

large effect ($d = 3.127$) indicate a significant difference in pronunciation skills before and after using the IPA symbols. After treatment, the student's pronunciation proficiency skills improved significantly. This means there is a significant difference in pronunciation skills before and after using the IPA symbols. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected.

The result shows that the level of pronunciation skills of the students before and after using the IPA symbols had a clear difference, with the pre-test showing did not meet expectation results and the post-test showing satisfactory results, which shows the student's progress is good. Moreover, Por and Fong (2011) emphasize that using phonetic symbols provides valuable guidance to students in understanding pronunciation. Students receive immediate and individualized feedback by comparing the sounds of model pronunciation with their pronunciation and referring to the displayed phonetic symbols. This enables them to approximate the correct pronunciations more effectively. The presence of phonetic symbols also facilitates students in predicting the accurate sounds in English, ultimately improving their pronunciation skills and boosting their confidence in speaking English.

Additionally, research suggests that students who receive pronunciation training are more likely to extend their knowledge and improve their accuracy in producing sounds that were not explicitly taught (Hardison, 2004; Ramírez-Verdugo, 2006). It is important to note that learning the International Phonetic Alphabet (IPA) alone does not guarantee flawless pronunciation. However, it does serve as a valuable tool for addressing pronunciation difficulties and reducing the number of mispronunciations caused by inconsistencies in English spelling conventions (Arleo, 1993). Moreover, a study by Lintunen (2013) demonstrated that students who could recognize and utilize IPA symbols exhibited greater confidence and better pronunciation skills than those who did not know IPA.

Table 2. Significant Difference in Pronunciation Skills before and after Using the IPA Symbols

Similar to the study of Heriansyah et al. (2021), articulation with the proper and appropriate input helps improve the learning process. Increased practice revolving around rhythm and intonation while focusing on realistic conversation helps develop articulatory phonetics necessary for communication with proper pronunciation (Gilakjani, 2011). Likewise, a study by Kang (2017) found that using IPA symbols in pronunciation instruction improved the pronunciation accuracy of Korean learners of English. These studies suggest that using IPA symbols can be an effective tool for language teachers who desire to help their students boost their pronunciation skills. By providing learners with a clear and consistent system for representing English sounds, IPA symbols can help learners develop a more accurate and nuanced understanding of English phonetics, which can help them produce more accurate and intelligible speech. As well as the study entitled 'Impact of IPA symbols' showed that there was a significant impact of IPA symbols on those students' spelling commands who were taught IPA as compared to those who were not taught (Fareeha, 2015); cited in (Qadir & Rizwan, 2020).

Further, the result of the study coincided with the results of various studies (Danga, 2022; Riza & Kawakib, 2021; Wah, 2016), which also found that using IPA symbols is effective in the students' pronunciation skills. However, these studies used different interventions to enhance pronunciation skills, such as Pronundroid-IPA pronunciation application (Danga, 2022); drill teaching method using the Oxford pocket dictionary (Riza & Kawakib, 2021); flashcards and blending exercises (Wah, 2016). In addition, other grade levels were involved in each study.

Lastly, since IPA symbols can significantly improve students' pronunciation skills, curriculum developers could incorporate more phonetic symbols into language learning materials, especially in sections focusing on pronunciation. On the other hand, teachers

Mean Scores		Mean Difference	Computed t-value	p	Cohen's <i>d</i>	Remark
Pre-test	Post-test					
29.92	37.88	7.96	12.466	.000	3.127	Significant

could use IPA symbols as a teaching tool to help them understand and practice pronunciation. This could be particularly useful in language laboratories or interactive learning environments where students receive immediate feedback (Smith, 2022; Kid World Citizen, 2018). Alternatively, policymakers could consider these findings when developing language education policies. They may advocate for including phonetic symbols in language learning standards or teaching training programs (Kid World Citizen, 2018; Maine Department of Education, 2023).

Conclusion

The following are the conclusions based on the findings:

This study has shown the level of effectiveness of using IPA symbols on the pronunciation skills of Grade 12 students. It can be gleaned that the students initially struggled with their English pronunciation. After using IPA symbols in teaching, students' mean value increased from the pre-test to the post-test, as shown in its descriptive equivalence. Thus, the difference signifies an improvement in students' pronunciation skills.

The study results showed that IPA symbols are essential before and after the test. This makes it more evident that participants' proficiency in pronunciation improved when they received treatment using IPA symbols. Grade 12 students place a significant value on the efficiency of using IPA symbols. Considering everything, phonetic symbols seem to have their place in pronunciation skills. Indeed, achieving improved English pronunciation, particularly concerning consonants and vowels, necessitates an appropriate approach. Using IPA symbols has been shown to impact students' pronunciation development. It can also be concluded that phonetic knowledge can improve pronunciation skills. Additionally, students should be attentive to their pronunciation learning strategies, as their methods can significantly influence their progress in this area. Students can enhance their pronunciation by actively engaging in practical strategies and techniques.

The study's findings imply that using IPA symbols in teaching is significant for teachers and students in real-world language instruction and learning contexts. For teachers, the results suggest that incorporating IPA symbols into their teaching methods can significantly improve students' pronunciation skills. Teachers may use IPA symbols as a consistent reference for teaching the sounds in English. They may also design activities that require students to use these symbols, such as transcription exercises or pronunciation drills. This may make the learning process more interactive and engaging, thus promoting better understanding and retention. For students, the study emphasizes the significance of being proactive in their pronunciation learning strategies. By actively engaging with IPA symbols and using them as a reference in their self-study, students may independently work on improving their pronunciation. They may use these symbols to understand English sounds better and practice them on their own.

The study is limited to senior high school students of a private school only. It excludes students of other year levels, public and private schools, tertiary education students, and other age brackets. Consequently, the conclusions are only valid for comparative purposes within the study. The study's findings are restricted to the population of the same criteria. It is necessary to conduct follow-up studies focusing on the factors not included in this study for a more comprehensive understanding of the effectiveness of using IPA symbols in enhancing pronunciation skills within the Philippine English curriculum. Future researches may employ a true experimental research design, which includes control groups and random assignment that can help establish stronger cause-and-effect relationships. It also encourages utilizing qualitative research designs or mixed-methods approaches to provide deeper insights and reinforce the study's results by combining numerical data with detailed and contextual information.

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